

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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1 Executive summary

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to evaluate citizen-science impacts. The objectives of this document are to define the eight multimedia resources (with subtitles in the relevant languages) and policy briefs presenting general and region-specific recommendations related to measuring the impact of citizen science.

The major results, or outcomes, of the project to be highlighted by these resources are:

- 1) an innovative **toolbox** to measure citizen-science impact on the following domains:
 - a. society
 - b. governance (including democracy and policy)
 - c. the economy
 - d. the environment
 - e. science and technology
- 2) a set of **recommendations, guidelines, and indicators** for measuring citizen-science impact (using nature-based solutions as initial case study)
- 3) a **generalisation blueprint** for extending and transfer project outcomes to other domains beyond *nature-based solutions* (NBSs) and the environment

The target audiences for the dissemination of results and the outputs of this document are:

- Civic educators and scientists as project managers
- Public authorities and decision makers (including policy makers)
- Researchers and scientists
- Citizens' networks

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to evaluate citizen-science impacts. The test and validation of these tools focus on the area of *nature-based solutions* (NBSs), defined by the *International Union for Conservation of Nature* (IUCN) as “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits”.

The MICS project specifically aims to:

1. provide comprehensive, participatory and inclusive metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts;
2. implement an impact-assessment knowledge-base through toolboxes for methods application, information visualisation, and delivery to decision makers, citizens and researchers;
3. improve the effectiveness of nature-based solutions through test-site development and citizen-science tool validation;
4. generate new approaches that strengthen the role of citizen science in supporting research and development;
5. foster a citizen-science approach to increase the extent to which scientific evidence is taken up by policy makers through recommendations and guidelines.

The result is an integrated platform where these metrics and instruments are available for use by anyone involved in a citizen-science project wanting to understand its impact, whether at the planning stage or several years after the project’s conclusion. This platform is validated by pilot testing in four test and validation sites across Europe. These sites explore the applicability of MICS impact-assessment tools in regions with differing needs, contexts, and approaches to nature-based solutions (NBS), and with various levels of citizen-science application. For example, in Western Europe, river restoration is increasingly carried out within an ecosystem-based management framework at river or catchment scale; in Southern Europe, river restoration tends to be issue-specific with some ecosystem relevance; in Central and Eastern Europe, river restoration is about ecosystem protection and related to existing infrastructure. The four test and validation sites selected are in the UK, Italy, Hungary and Romania.

2.2 MICS’ major results

The main result of the project is an integrated platform, where MICS metrics and instruments are available for use by anyone involved in a citizen-science project wanting to understand its impact, whether at the planning stage, during the project or after the project’s conclusion.

Hence, the major outputs of the project for dissemination and exploitation are predicted to be:

- a **toolbox** (WP3) to measure citizen-science impact on the following domains:
 - a. society
 - b. governance (including democracy and policy)
 - c. the economy
 - d. the environment
 - e. science and technology

- a set of **recommendations, guidelines, and indicators** (WP2) for measuring citizen-science impact (using NBSs as initial case study)
- a **generalisation blueprint** (WP2) for extending and transfer outcomes to other domains beyond NBSs and the environment

More precisely, these outputs will consist of:

- MICS tools: the MICS web-platform, algorithms, new methods, and hosting servers for data, tutorials and educational materials to support and increase awareness;
- impact-assessment systems;
- repositories of open information;
- a data interoperability service;
- metrics and indicators on citizen-science impact;
- data collected through the MICS platform;
- a set of recommendations guidelines and training materials.

The multimedia resources detailed in this document are designed to support and disseminate these outputs to intended stakeholders, ensuring successful exploitation of the project's results and increased sustainability of the platform.

This relates to the exploitation roadmap of MICS, outlined in **D5.9 Update to the PEDR**, which is included here for ease of access.

Table 1 Exploitation Roadmap (from D5.9 Update to the PEDR)

Stakeholder	How to contact	Marketing materials	Anticipated outcome	Short / Medium / Long term goals
Project managers	Email lists, including ECSA	Video of the platform	Increased interest in completing the MICS impact assessment	As the project nears completion, efforts should still be made to disseminate to project managers, to ensure the platform is used beyond the lifetime of the project
Decision makers	Email, LinkedIn	White paper	Increased interest in citizen science, NBS and impact assessment	With increased use of the MICS tools by project managers, the utility of citizen science and NBS will be demonstrated in the medium – long term.
Researchers	Email, conferences	Publications, including posters and oral presentations	Uptake of citizen science practises	In the medium to long term, the positive impact of citizen science should be demonstrated, encouraging more researchers to use citizen science practises, particularly towards the SDGs
Citizen scientists	Email, social media	Newsletters, images / videos from case studies	Improved understanding of how citizen science contributes to SDGs	With an improved understanding of the impact of citizen science, the engagement and motivation of citizen scientists should improve in the short term
General public	Social media, interviews and articles	Video of the MICS project	Awareness of citizen science	Through wide and regular sharing of the MICS video, social media posts and sustained communication in blogs and interviews, MICS can play a role in improving citizen science uptake in the general public

Press and media	Social media, events including final project event and Impact workshop	Videos, images, interviews, presentations	Publicity for MICS project and outcomes	In the short term, the press and media can be used to encourage further utility of the platform by project managers, as well as an interest in citizen science in the general public. In the medium and short term they can aid in the dissemination of milestones hit and the use of the MICS tools by decision makers.
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3 Multimedia resources

3.1 General MICS video

In collaboration with Science Animated - a communication agency who develop engaging and accessible animations based on scientific research - we are producing a 90 second 2D animation to explain “How can we measure the impact of citizen science”.

The animation will use primarily brand colours and font, and has the following description:

“The MICS project [mics.tools], coordinated by Earthwatch Europe, has developed a state-of-the-art tool for assessing citizen science’s impact. The free-to-use, open-access platform is available to anyone looking to improve their impact assessment. MICS uses 200 variables to determine the impact of a citizen-science project in five areas: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. Five case studies explore how citizen scientists work together to monitor nature-based solutions and protect the environment.”

Consisting of thirteen scenes – detailed below in Table 2 – the video has been designed to highlight the key findings of the MICS project to a wide audience. As noted in the exploitation roadmap (Table 1) the MICS project video is anticipated to improve citizen science uptake in the general public. The language used in video script has been carefully worded to ensure the information can be understood by all of the project stakeholders; citizen scientists as well as researchers and public authorities. The video will include subtitles to ensure individuals who are hard of hearing have access to the information, and will be translated (orally and with subtitles) into the relevant case-study languages (Italian, Hungarian and Romanian). Moreover, the imagery used in the animation will be as inclusive as possible - note in scene two “*Show people in the park of mixed ages, genders, and ethnicities*” – and the script will be read by a female.

The final version of the video will be produced in Jul 2022. Once finalised, it will be hosted within the homepage of the MICS platform to ensure visibility. It will also be hosted on the [MICS YouTube channel](#), and the [Science Animated YouTube channel](#). We will disseminate the video across our social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn) as well as via the final MICS newsletter.

Table 2 MICS project video story board

Scene and Text	Scene description
1.	Open with the MICS logo to establish the project from the beginning of the video. The logo fades.
2. Citizen science involves members of the public in the generation and application of scientific knowledge.	<p>New scene. Show a public park, which should include trees (with birds perched on branches) and a pond. Show people in the park of mixed ages, genders, and ethnicities. Show two people birdwatching using binoculars. Show another two people pond dipping – one person using a net and another looking at sample tray. Show one person crouched down looking at a quadrant on the grass. The person should be holding a clipboard and writing on it.</p>
3. The MICS project developed methods and tools to help citizen-science projects measure and achieve their impacts.	<p>New scene. Show a desktop computer and at the top of the screen show the MICS logo. On the screen show a colourful flowchart appearing element by element containing nondistinctive text</p>
4. It included several case studies which brought together community groups and local authorities to co-design new citizen-science initiatives around nature-based solutions .	<p>New scene. Cut to a world map similar to the reference image below. One by one, pins (in the style of google maps) are dropped on the map. Two are dropped in the UK, one is in Hungary, one is in Italy and one in Romania. On nature-based, zoom in on the pin on Italy to transition into the next scene.</p>
5. In Italy, school children and other locals monitored the effects of wetlands on the water quality of the Marzenego River. They even developed their own method for measuring levels of bacteria!	<p>New scene. Show a riverside scene, similar to the reference image below. At the top of the segment, it says Marzenego river, Italy. Show a group of school aged children using devices similar to the ones in the below reference images to measure the water quality</p>
6. In Romania, citizen scientists investigated the effects of Danube wetland restoration on water quality and bank stability.	<p>New scene. Show a wetlands scene, similar to the reference image below. At the top of this segment, it says Danube Wetlands, Romania. Two people are stood in the shallow water wearing rain boots and using a measuring devise like that in the image below.</p>
7. The project in Hungary surveyed water quality and biodiversity to promote the restoration of Creek Rákos.	<p>New scene. Show a creek scene, similar to the reference image below. At the top of this segment, it says Creek Rákos, Hungary. The creek is lined by long grass. A person is crouched next to the water. In the creek there are several lily pads, and a frog is jumping from one to another.</p>

<p>8. In the UK, MICS worked with two established citizen-science projects, Outfall Safari and Riverfly, to evaluate their impacts.</p>	<p>New scene. Show a zoomed in river scene similar to the reference image below – show a small amount of pollutants entering the river from the pipes.</p>
<p>9. The MICS project developed a platform to help all citizen-science projects assess their impacts, and reach their full potential.</p>	
<p>10. MICS considers the impact of citizen science in several areas: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology.</p>	<p>New scene. Show MICS icons for domains e.g. economy</p>
<p>11. MICS found that citizen-science projects improve democratic engagement and promote a scientific mentality, contributing to achieving the UN's sustainable development goals and promoting a sustainable future.</p>	<p>New scene. Show 4 people by a river, one of the people should be crouched down by a tree they have just planted. On democratic engagement, an arrow appears pointing at the person who is crouched down. At the base of the arrow there is a speech bubble, with the words Citizen Scientist inside. Similarly, a speech bubble and arrow appears pointing at one of the people standing by the river, with the words Local Government Leader inside the speech bubble. Another speech bubble and arrow appears pointing at one of the people standing by the river, with the words Local Water Authority inside the speech bubble.</p> <p>The speech bubbles and text vanish. On sustainable, the words Lifelong Education, Good Health and Wellbeing, Clean Water and Sanitation, Sustainable Communities, and Life on Land are overlaid on the screen. They are equally spaced apart.</p>
<p>12. Visit mics.tools to find out more</p>	<p>New Scene. The MICS Project is a collaboration between six European partners</p>
<p>13.</p>	<p>New scene. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711.</p>

3.2 MICS platform video

Science Animated are also collaborating with MICS to produce a 90 second 2D animation to explain “MICS: a platform to measure the impact of citizen science”.

As before, the animation will use primarily brand colours and font, and has the following description:

“The MICS project has developed state-of-the-art tools for assessing citizen science’s impact. AI technology helps analyse over 200 variables to determine the impact of a project in five areas: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. The free-to-use, open-access platform is available to anyone looking to improve their impact assessment.”

Consisting of eleven scenes – detailed below in Table 3 – the video has been designed to highlight the functionality of the MICS platform.

As noted in the exploitation roadmap (Table 1) the MICS project video is anticipated to increase project coordinators’ interest in completing the MICS impact assessment. In comparison to the general MICS video, the language used in the platform video script is more technical, although still accessible to a wide audience. As before, the video will include subtitles to ensure individuals who are hard of hearing have access to the information and the script will be read by a female.

There are currently no plans to translate the MICS platform video into multiple languages. The platform itself has been developed in English, with the indicators and recommendations also written in English. It is, therefore, anticipated that users of the MICS platform will have a good understanding of the English language; whereas viewers of the more general MICS video may have an interest in citizen science without being able to speak English.

Much like the general MICS video, the final version of the platform video will be produced in July 2022. Once finalised, it will be hosted within the homepage of the MICS platform to ensure visibility. It will also be hosted on the [MICS YouTube channel](#), and the [Science Animated YouTube channel](#). We will disseminate the video across our social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn) as well as via the final MICS newsletter.

Table 3 MICS platform video storyboard

Scene and Text	Scene description
1.	Open with the MICS logo to establish the project from the beginning of the video.
<p>2. It has never been easy to accurately measure the impact of citizen science... until now!</p> <p>The MICS project has developed a web-based platform to do just that.</p>	<p>New scene. Two scientists are sat at a desk, each with a computer in front of them. They are typing on the keyboard. They're in an office space.</p>
<p>3. With the platform's help, users can assess whether a project has had an impact on several domains: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology.</p>	<p>New scene A series of icons are overlaid on the screen. E.g. on economy:</p>
<p>4. The MICS platform is free to use, and any citizen-science project can register on the platform to assess its impact. All results are available to the public.</p>	<p>New scene. Show a computer screen. On the computer screen in time with the VO show the following text and circular images from left to right:</p> <p><i>Note: Put a cross over the pound sign to represent lack of cost</i></p>
<p>5. The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users can choose from.</p>	
<p>6. These questions assess hundreds of indicators and are based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks such as the ECSA characteristics of citizen science.</p>	<p>Continue from previous scene. On hundreds of indicators, words will appear overlaid on the scene, equidistance apart: education; participation; engagement; diversity; communication; empowerment; justice</p>
<p>7. Each project's answers are analysed by a series of artificial-intelligence algorithms, which generate impact scores.</p>	<p>New scene. On artificial intelligence, an icon similar to below will overlay on the screen. The icon will be pulsing, getting a little bigger and a little smaller every other second.</p>
<p>8. The MICS platform also provides projects with recommendations on improving impact across several domains and an assessment of their impact on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.</p>	<p>New scene. Cut to a person sat in front of a laptop, only their arms are visible as it is a close shot, similar to the reference image below. The person is typing in lines of code which are appearing onscreen.</p>

<p>9. The MICS platform can analyse a project at any stage of development and can be used to inform ongoing activities to improve impact.</p>	<p>The person continues typing. On improve, the coding on the computer screen vanishes and is replaced with a green tick mark.</p>
<p>10. Visit mics.tools to find out more</p>	<p>New Scene. The MICS Project is a collaboration between six European partners</p>
<p>11.</p>	<p>New scene. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711</p>

3.3 MICS platform “how to” guide

Along with the videos, another key multimedia resource featured on the homepage of the MICS platform will be the “how to” guide.

This pdf document will provide clear instructions to project coordinators on how to navigate through the MICS platform. It will walk users step by step through the process of logging in, or registering on the platform; creating a project page; navigating through the assessment tool, with prompts for how to answer questions, how to find help and information text via the appropriate links, and how to access the “where to find help” page of the platform. The guide will also enable users to access the impact summary of their project once the assessment has been completed, and how to print or share versions of the summary for their own dissemination purposes. The “how to” guide will also signpost users to further help and guidance, found at <https://about.mics.tools>.

Although the “how to” guide was not included in the exploitation roadmap, it is anticipated to function alongside the platform video to increase project coordinators’ interest in completing the MICS impact assessment. The language used is accessible for all audiences, designed to ease any technical challenges users may face when navigating through the MICS platform.

A draft version of the first page of the guide is shown in Figure 1 below. The content is subject to updating as the final developments to the platform are made before launching.

Figure 1 MICS platform “how to” guide page 1

MICS platform how-to guide

Use the buttons below to navigate to the relevant section of the how-to guide

Further guidance and help can be found at <https://about.mics.tools>

Log in or Register

The “Log in” and “Register” pages can be accessed from the right-hand side of the header of the MICS platform and from the left menu-bar on the home page (see orange arrows in the image below).

Social media vs email and password log in. Users can choose to log in with either a social media account or an email and password. In both cases the only information kept about the user is their name and email address. Logging in with social media is quicker but if several users will need to edit the same project it's best to register an email and password so that log in details can be shared among the team (each project can only be edited by one account).

3.4 MICS training resources

The “impact indicator explorer” (detailed in **D3.5 Participatory adaptive, personalised information-delivery web platform, period - 2 prototype (P2P)**) will allow users to determine for themselves what the most appropriate tool within the MICS platform is for them; based on their understanding of impact and the stage of their project.

An experienced project coordinator with a good understanding of impact assessment, for example, may use the platform to complete the MICS impact assessment and receive an output with recommendations for improving their project’s impact. However, an individual new to the field of citizen science, with limited experience in developing impactful projects, may wish to access educational materials.

Much like publications and presentations, these resources aim to demonstrate the positive impact of citizen science to researchers, encouraging more researchers to use citizen science practises, particularly towards the sustainable development goals. The language used will be appropriate for citizen science practitioners.

Two partners, IHE-Delft and RRC, are developing multimedia training materials to be hosted on the MICS platform. These consist of the following three courses.

1. Measuring the Impacts of River Restoration/ NBS projects

A one-day course led by RRC, this course aims to provide an overview of what impact is, why it is important to measure, and how to measure it in river restoration / NBS focused projects

2. Co-designing citizen science for impact

This two/three-day course led by IHE-Delft will provide detailed introduction to the Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology light for co-designing citizen science initiatives for impact with diverse stakeholders

3. Co-evaluating citizen science impacts: a one day course led by IHE-Delft

A one-day course led by IHE-Delft which will introduce the MICS impact journey approach for co-evaluating the impacts of citizen science initiatives (at any stage of their life time)

Further details of the two training courses currently being developed by IHE-Delft are provided in Table 4 and Table 5 below.

Table 4 Co-designing citizen science for impact

Course title	Co-designing citizen science for impact
Aim of course	Provide a detailed introduction to the methodology for co-designing citizen science for impact
Learning outcomes	<p>Course participants will be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differentiate between different forms of co-designing citizen science projects; • Outline the steps of the citizen science co-design methodology; • Use the co-design methodology for citizen science projects; • Discuss what the 'co-design of citizen science projects for impact' entails
Course description	<p>Citizen science is increasingly recognised as a multi-stakeholder phenomenon. This nuanced understanding often goes hand in hand with questions regarding the control over and participation in the process of setting up and running citizen science initiatives. Involving and managing diverse stakeholders from the start and over time can be challenging; as a result, achieving impact with citizen science can be elusive.</p> <p>Based on the best practice generated by the Ground Truth 2.0 project for co-designing full-scale citizen observatories, the MICS project adapted this approach for co-designing citizen science activities for impact, in the context of nature-based solutions. The resulting co-design methodology focuses on generating citizen science activities that are based on a sound understanding of the social context, set up to address jointly agreed societal challenges and with a clear focus on impact. Based on guiding principles, this approach provides a coherent process for the joint development of the purpose, scope and implementation of citizen activities with citizen scientists and other key stakeholders.</p> <p>This course will introduce participants to the co-design of citizen science initiatives and provides them with a sound understanding of the methodology and how it can be applied in different contexts and settings.</p> <p>The short course is designed as problem-based active learning and contains practical activities to illustrate what comes into play when co-designing citizen science projects with diverse stakeholders. During the course, participants will work in teams, each on the co-design of a specific citizen science project. Participants will be encouraged to share their own experience with citizen science and co-designing citizen science in particular, whether as participants or coordinators. Case studies and lessons learned of existing citizen science projects, including case studies from the MICS project, are incorporated throughout the course. This provides participants with opportunities to learn how each step in the co-design methodology can be implemented in different contexts.</p>
Target Audience	Citizens and professionals from academia, the private sector, public sector or civil society with an interest in setting up citizen science initiatives using co-design

Table 5 Co-evaluating citizen science impacts

Course title	Co-evaluating citizen science impacts
Aim of course	Provide an introduction to the MICS impact journey approach for co-evaluating the impacts of citizen science initiatives (any stage of their life time)
Learning outcomes	<p>Course participants will be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss what measuring the impacts of citizen science initiatives entails and how stakeholders can be involved in this; • Identify the activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts of a citizen science initiative • Construct an Impact Journey map for a citizen science initiative; • Develop and apply an impact monitoring strategy for a citizen science initiative, together with citizen science stakeholders
Course description	<p>While citizen science is steadily increasing in popularity across sectors, impact assessment rarely forms a central pillar of citizen science initiatives. This is despite the fact that one of the key requirements for realising the potential of citizen science is evidence and demonstration of its impact and value. A comprehensive impact assessment of citizen science initiatives can be difficult to implement, with a broad range of factors influencing impacts and a diverse group of stakeholders involved.</p> <p>To provide practical approach for ongoing and new citizen science initiatives, the MICS project developed and tested the Impact Journey co-evaluation approach. This approach is comprised of three main stages: a context analysis, the design and validation of the Impact Journey, and Planning, Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning. These stages allow for the identification of relevant domains of change, expected outcomes, and expected impacts; formulating strategies for achieving desired changes; determining cause and effect relationships; and documenting causal assumptions.</p> <p>This course will introduce participants to the Impact Journey co-evaluation approach, and provide them with a solid understanding of how the approach can be implemented in different citizen science contexts and settings.</p> <p>The short course is designed as problem-based active learning and contains practical activities to illustrate what comes into play when designing impact assessments of citizen science projects with diverse stakeholders. During the course, participants will work in teams, each on the impact journey for a specific citizen science project. Participants will be encouraged to share their own experience with citizen science impact assessment in particular, whether as participants or coordinators. Case studies and lessons learned of existing citizen science projects, including case studies from the MICS project, are incorporated throughout the course. This provides participants with opportunities to learn how each step in the Impact Journey approach can be implemented in different contexts.</p>
Target Audience	Citizen science practitioners from academia, the private sector, public sector or civil society with an interest in measuring the impact of citizen science initiatives

3.5 Four factsheets detailing region-specific recommendations related to citizen science and nature-based solutions

The MICS case study sites explore the applicability of MICS impact-assessment tools in regions with differing needs, contexts, and approaches to nature-based solutions, and with various levels of citizen-science application. As described, in Western Europe, river restoration is carried out within an ecosystem-based management framework; in Southern Europe, river restoration tends to be issue-specific with some ecosystem relevance; in Central and Eastern Europe, river restoration is about ecosystem protection and related to existing infrastructure. The four test and validation sites are, therefore, in the UK, Italy, Hungary and Romania.

Rather than “policy briefs”, which are targeted towards public authorities and decision makers, case study leads produced “factsheets” to encourage citizen-science uptake within their case study regions.

These factsheets present general and region-specific recommendations regarding citizen science and NBS in English, Italian, Hungarian and Romanian. The language is used suitable for a general audience, designed to improve citizen science uptake within the case study regions. The images include citizen scientists who have taken part in activities, fostering a sense of ownership of the project.

Figure 2 Citizen science and river restoration in the U.K.

Citizen Science for Rivers

How citizen science can support river management and restoration

What is Citizen Science?
Citizen science is defined as the participation of volunteers (i.e. people not involved as part of their employment) in environmental research and monitoring. This has the dual benefit of allowing individuals to contribute to scientific research while also engaging with and educating people. Citizen science projects are often set up by professionals (e.g. project managers working at wildlife NGO's or conservation organisations), who define the projects aims and objectives. Volunteers then contribute data to the project. This approach, referred to as contributory citizen science, is widely used in the UK. But there are many different forms of citizen science that you may wish to consider.

Individuals and local communities play a critical role in all phases of river management and restoration; citizen science is one aspect of this. Citizen scientists carry out environmental research, river monitoring, restoration work, lead on projects, and more. The work carried out by citizen scientists helps support river management decisions. Involving citizens in river projects often has multiple impacts, not only for those involved, but also on society, the environment, and science itself.

Why Use Citizen Science to Support River Management and Restoration?
Increased urbanisation and climate change mean that our rivers are under increasing pressure, and we face difficult decisions regarding how to best manage them long-term. Citizen science can help us to address these challenges by:

- **Project Design:** Engaging local communities in the design phase of projects ensures local knowledge is taken into account at the earliest possible stage. This will improve the quality and resilience of restoration projects.
- **Data Collection:** By gathering scientific data (through monitoring activities) citizen scientists help to determine the current state of river systems and allow us to make informed management decisions.
- **Cost-Effective and Sustainable:** Community involvement can help increase the scope and ambition of river restoration projects; citizen science is a cost-effective way to carry out long-term monitoring.
- **Engagement and Education:** Citizen science projects provides a means of engaging with a diverse range of people and increase their knowledge, awareness, and involvement.
- **Reconnecting People with Nature:** Citizen involvement helps reconnect local communities with nature and engender a feeling of stewardship towards rivers.
- **Vision and Leadership:** Citizen scientists can take responsibility for leading on projects and offer insights that help drive future improvements.

Contributory, Collaborative, or Co-Created?
There are three primary approaches to citizen science. These include:
Contributory: Citizens are only involved in data collection. The project design, aims and objectives, and activities, are decided by scientists/project managers.
Collaborative: Citizens contribute data and may help in project design, but the aims and objectives and activities are decided upon by scientists/project managers.
Co-created: Citizens are actively engaged in all stages of the project, working alongside project managers to identify the aims and objectives and agree upon activities, in addition to being involved in data collection.

Selecting which of these approaches to use will depend on the nature of the research project. For projects involving environmental monitoring that have a clear end-use for the data, the contributory model will likely be the most applicable format. However, collaborative and co-created projects help to:

- **Greater Commitment:** Community-led projects benefit from individuals feeling that they have a 'stake' in the project.
- **Increased Longevity:** Where repeat monitoring is necessary communities will likely be more willing to commit to this.
- **Better Informed:** Having the community involved in project planning at an early stage means local knowledge can be taken into account at an early stage, and a more robust set of aims and objectives formulated.
- **Increased Scope:** Local involvement may help in the identification of additional issues or monitoring opportunities not foreseen by other stakeholders.

Case Study – Anglers Riverfly Monitoring Initiative (ARMI)

Pollution is a key problem affecting our rivers and can enter from a variety of different pathways. The Riverfly Partnerships ARMI citizen science initiative is a simple, standardized methodology that enables volunteers to monitor river water quality and detect pollution events by scoring the occurrence and relative abundance of different insect groups known as 'riverflies'. The project has been successful in gaining support from local interest groups, such as anglers, and is now carried out on hundreds of river sites throughout the UK.

Key benefits:

- The initiative has developed the participants skills in co-ordinating the planning, initiation and implementation of their own restoration schemes;
- Cost-effective collection of long-term datasets;
- Better alignment between the monitoring efforts of citizens and regulatory bodies;
- Increased detection and reporting of pollution events;
- Increased feeling of stewardship amongst citizens;
- Inspired scientific interest in a new audience.

In some ARMI groups citizen scientists have taken a more active role in project decision making and have worked with project managers to define additional aims and objectives. This transition from *contributory* to *collaborative* citizen science has resulted in the creation of new monitoring initiatives – such as the Extended Riverfly – which aim to further challenge and expand interest in the project.

More information about how to establish successful citizen science projects for river management and restoration can be found on the [Catchment Based Approach \(CaBA\) Website](#).

An important step in developing successful citizen science initiatives is to monitor the projects impacts to promote further growth and development. To get best-practice advice on how to monitor the impact of your citizen science initiative visit the [Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science \(MICS\) project Website](#).

Figure 3 Citizen science and river restoration in Italy

La citizen science per i fiumi e le zone umide

*Come la citizen science può aiutare nella gestione e riqualificazione dei fiumi
(in generale per tutti gli ecosistemi d'acqua dolce)*

Che cos'è la Citizen Science?
Per citizen science si intende la partecipazione di volontari (cioè persone non coinvolte nell'ambito del loro lavoro) in attività di ricerca (es. monitoraggio). Ciò ha il duplice vantaggio di consentire alle persone di contribuire alla ricerca scientifica e allo stesso tempo di incrementare le loro conoscenze (educazione permanente – lifelong learning). I progetti di citizen science sono spesso organizzati da professionisti (ad es. ricercatori, project manager che lavorano presso una ONG per la fauna selvatica o un'organizzazione per la conservazione), che definiscono gli scopi e gli obiettivi del progetto. I volontari, quindi, contribuiscono al progetto solo con la raccolta dati. Questo approccio, denominato Citizen science contributiva oggi è ampiamente utilizzato, ma ci sono diversi livelli di coinvolgimento dei cittadini che dovrebbero essere presi in considerazione.

I cittadini e le comunità locali possono giocare un ruolo chiave in tutte le fasi della gestione e riqualificazione dei fiumi; la citizen science crea grandi opportunità per questa collaborazione.

I cittadini scienziati possono svolgere ricerche in campo ambientale, monitorare i fiumi, fare lavori di ripristino, fare da guida su alcuni progetti ed altro ancora. I cittadini che partecipano ai progetti di citizen science possono essere di grande aiuto nel processo decisionale di gestione e riqualificazione dei fiumi.

Il coinvolgimento dei cittadini nei progetti di riqualificazione e gestione dei fiumi ha benefici multipli, non solo per le persone coinvolte, ma anche per la società, per l'ambiente e per la scienza.

In quale modo la citizen science può supportare la gestione e riqualificazione degli ecosistemi di acque dolci?
A causa dell'aumento dell'urbanizzazione i nostri fiumi sono sottoposti a una pressione crescente e di conseguenza dobbiamo affrontare decisioni difficili per gestirli in modo sostenibile, soprattutto nel lungo termine. La citizen science può aiutarci ad affrontare queste sfide:

- **Progettazione:** il coinvolgimento delle comunità locali nella fase di progettazione garantisce che la conoscenza locale venga integrata fin dalle prime fasi. Ciò apporterà notevoli benefici alla qualità e alla resilienza dei progetti di riqualificazione.
- **Raccolta dati:** raccogliendo dati scientifici attraverso attività di monitoraggio, i cittadini aiutano a conoscere lo stato attuale degli ecosistemi d'acqua dolce e di conseguenza consentono di prendere decisioni più accurate.
- **Economico e sostenibile:** il coinvolgimento della comunità può contribuire a raggiungere obiettivi più ambiziosi nei progetti di riqualificazione degli ecosistemi d'acqua dolce; ad esempio la citizen science può contribuire in modo significativo nel monitoraggio a lungo termine.
- **Coinvolgimento ed educazione:** i progetti di citizen science sono un utile strumento per coinvolgere un elevato numero di persone e dare l'opportunità di accrescere le loro conoscenze e consapevolezza dell'ambiente in cui vivono.
- **Riconnettere le persone con la natura:** il coinvolgimento dei cittadini aiuta a riconnettere le comunità locali con la natura e a generare un senso di appartenenza al territorio prendendosene cura.
- **Visione e Leadership:** i cittadini nei progetti di citizen science possono assumersi la responsabilità di gestire progetti ed offrire conoscenze utili ad indirizzare le nuove sfide per il futuro.

Contributivo, Collaborativo, o Co-creativo?
Ci sono tre principali approcci alla citizen science e sono:

Contributivo: i cittadini sono coinvolti solo nella raccolta dei dati. Il design del progetto, gli scopi, gli obiettivi e le attività sono decisi dagli scienziati/managers responsabili del progetto.

Collaborativo: i cittadini forniscono dati e aiutano nella progettazione, ma gli obiettivi principali e le attività vengono decisi dagli scienziati/managers del progetto.

Co-creativo: i cittadini sono attivamente coinvolti in tutte le fasi del progetto, lavorando a fianco dei project manager per identificare gli scopi e gli obiettivi e concordare le attività, oltre a partecipare alla raccolta dei dati.

La scelta di quale di questi approcci utilizzare dipenderà dalla natura del progetto di ricerca. I progetti collaborativi e co-creati aiutano a:

- **Maggior impegno:** i progetti guidati dalla comunità traggono vantaggio dal fatto che le persone si sentono più responsabilizzate.
- **Maggior longevità:** laddove è necessario ripetere il monitoraggio, le comunità saranno probabilmente più disposte a impegnarsi a lungo termine.
- **Migliore informazione:** Avere la comunità coinvolta fin dalle prime fasi del progetto permette di prendere in considerazione la conoscenza locale rendendo gli obiettivi e gli scopi del progetto più solidi.
- **Maggiore portata:** il coinvolgimento locale può aiutare nell'identificazione di problemi aggiuntivi o nel monitoraggio di opportunità non previste dalle Istituzioni preposte.

BOX CASO STUDIO – Il Marzenego e le sue oasi

Il caso studio del Marzenego ha avuto come obiettivo principale quello di programmare attività di monitoraggio allo scopo di misurare l'efficacia delle "Natural Base Solutions: Oasi/zone umide e golene vegetate, nel bacino del Marzenego. Assieme ai cittadini è stata definita una strategia di monitoraggio durante diversi incontri sia in presenza che online in cui sono stati identificati i parametri da misurare, le stazioni da monitorare, le tempistiche e le attività a cui i cittadini volevano partecipare. Negli incontri c'è stata anche la partecipazione attiva di alcune Istituzioni come ad esempio il Consorzio Acquisorgive, l'ARPAV, i Comuni di Noale e Martellago, Veritas e alcuni rappresentanti delle categorie professionali (es. Ingegneri).

In un secondo tempo, dal Novembre 2020 a maggio 2022, sono state coinvolte nel progetto MICS, per le misure dei nitrati, fosfati, torbidità etc., le Scuole del comune di Noale, sia elementari che medie per un totale di 21 classi e circa 500 studenti di V elementare e I media. Contemporaneamente si è aggiunta anche la partecipazione della Scuola Secondaria di Mirano (IIS LeviPonti) che oltre ad effettuare il monitoraggio, di cui sopra, hanno partecipato all'implementazione di una metodica semplificata per le misure batteriologiche di *Escherichia coli* confrontandole con i metodi ufficiali standardizzati.

Le attività più significative:

- Coordinamento e pianificazione fatte in collaborazione tra esperti e cittadini;
- Una significativa raccolta di dati sia lungo l'asta del Marzenego e del suo tributario il Draganziole che delle Oasi di Noale e Lycaena e la golena di Trebaseleghe.
- Collaborazione e incontro tra le scuole elementari e medie di Noale con la scuola Secondaria di Mirano (IIS LeviPonti)
- Implementazione di una metodologia semplificata per *Escherichia coli* in collaborazione con la scuola IIS LeviPonti;
- Validazione dei metodi di citizen science con i "metodi ufficiali" in collaborazione con la scuola IIS LeviPonti;
- Monitoraggio delle Oasi al fine di valutarne l'efficienza depurativa;
- Monitoraggio della vegetazione riparia;
- Partecipazione attiva dei cittadini nell'analisi degli impatti del progetto MICS
- Restituzione e analisi dei risultati nelle scuole di Noale
- Restituzione ed analisi dei risultati ai cittadini in un incontro online

Nel progetto MICS alcuni gruppi hanno assunto un ruolo attivo nel processo decisionale collaborando a stretto contatto con i ricercatori del progetto. Inoltre il forte coinvolgimento delle scuole ha portato notevoli benefici non solo al progetto, che in questo modo ha potuto raggiungere un elevato numero di famiglie e quindi di cittadini ma ha anche dato un ruolo sociale attivo alla scuola. Far parte di un progetto di citizen science assieme ad altre componenti della società ha aperto le porte della scuola ad una didattica non solo di tipo outdoor ma anche di coinvolgimento attivo nella conoscenza del territorio finalizzato ad una gestione futura più sostenibile.

Un passo importante nello sviluppo di iniziative di Citizen Science di successo è monitorare l'impatto dei progetti per promuovere ulteriore crescita e sviluppo. Per ottenere consigli sulle migliori pratiche per misurare l'impatto della tua iniziativa di Citizen Science, visita il sito web del progetto Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science (MICS).

Figure 4 Citizen science in Hungary

Civil tudomány a vízfolyásokért

Hogyan támogathatja a civil tudomány az vízfolyások vízgazdálkodási és helyreállítási tevékenységeit?

Mit is jelent a civil tudomány?
A civil tudománynak hívjuk az önkéntesek részvételét a környezeti kutatásban és monitoringban, akiknek ez nem a munkájuk része. Ez kettős előnnyel jár, mégpedig az egyén hozzájárul a tudományos kutatáshoz, emellett elkötelezi az embereket az ügy mellett, a vízfolyás iránt és bővíti a tudásukat ezen a téren.
A civil tudomány projekteket gyakran szakemberek szervezik (pl. projektmenedzserek pl. természetvédelmi civil szervezeteknél), akik meghatározzák a projekt céljait. Az önkéntesek pedig adatokkal járulnak hozzá a projekthez. Ezt a megközelítést hozzájáruló civil tudománynak is hívják, amely számos országban, például az Egyesült Királyságban is széles körben alkalmaznak. A civil tudománynak számos egyéb formája van még, amelyeket érdemes megfontolni.

Egyének és helyi közösségek fontos szerepet játszanak a vízfolyások vízgazdálkodásának és helyreállításának minden szakaszában, amelyekből az egyik a civil tudomány.
A civil tudósok környezeti kutatásban, vízfolyás monitoringban, helyreállítási munkákban, projekteket követnek és vezetnek, és még ennél is többet. A civil tudósok munkája segíti vízfolyásokkal kapcsolatos vízgazdálkodási döntések meghozatalát.
A civilek bevonása vízfolyásokkal kapcsolatos projektekre gyakran számos pozitív hatást von magával és nem csak a bevont egyének esetén, hanem a társadalom, ökológia és a tudomány terén is.

Miért alkalmazzuk a civil tudomány megközelítést a vízfolyások vízgazdálkodásának és helyreállításának támogatására?
A fokozódó urbanizáció és klímaváltozás fokozódó terhelésnek teszi ki a vízfolyásainkat is, így egyre bonyolultabb döntéseket hozni, hogyan tudunk a vízzel legjobban gazdálkodni, különösen hosszú távban gondolkodva.
A civil tudomány segíthet ezen kihívások kezelésében különösen az alábbi területeken:

- **Projekt tervezés:** A helyi közösségek elkötelezése a projektek tervezési fázisában biztosítja a helyi tudás becsatornázását már a lehető legkorábbi fázisban. Ez javítja a helyreállítási projektek minőségét és rugalmasságát.
- **Adatgyűjtés:** Tudományos adatok gyűjtésével (monitoring tevékenység során) a civil tudósok segítenek, hogy megbizonyosodjunk a vízfolyás aktuális állapotának bizonyos jellemzőiben és hogy ezt követően informált döntéseket hozhassunk.
- **Költséghatékonyság és fenntarthatóság:** A közösség bevonása segíthet a vízfolyás helyreállítási projektek spektrumát és ambícióját kiszélesíteni; a civil tudomány költséghatékony módja a hosszú távú monitoring megvalósításának.
- **Elköteleződés és oktatás:** A civil tudomány projekteket a legkülönbözőbb embereket tudják elkötelezni és növelni a tudásukat, érzékenységüket, valamint a bevonásukat.
- **Összekapcsolja az embereket a természettel:** A civilek bevonása elősegíti a helyi közösségek újbóli összekapcsolódását az őket körülvevő természeti környezettel, és felkelt az egyénekben a felelősségérzetet a vízfolyások védelme iránt.
- **Vízió és irányítás:** A civil tudósok vállalhatják a felelősséget a projektek vezetésében, valamint olyan meglátásokkal segíthetik azokat, amely elősegíthetik a jövőbeli fejlesztéseket.

Hozzájáruló, együttműködő, együtt-tervezett?
Alapvetően három megközelítés létezik a civil tudományban:
Hozzájáruló: A civileket bevonják az adatgyűjtésbe. A projekt tervezéséről, céljairól és a tevékenységeiről a tudósok, projektmenedzserek döntenek.
Együttműködő: A civilek segítenek az adatgyűjtésben, és a projektfejlesztésben segíthetnek, de a célok, tevékenységekben a tudósok, projektmenedzserek döntenek.
Együtt-tervezett: A civileket aktívan bevonják a projekt minden szakaszába együtt dolgozva a projektmenedzserekkel a célok meghatározásában, a tevékenységek kialakításában, illetve az adatgyűjtésbe is bevonják őket.

Hogy melyik megközelítést alkalmazzák, a kutatási projekt jellegén múlik. Azon projekteknél, ahol környezeti monitoring a cél és világos az adatok végső felhasználása, ott a hozzájáruló modell, amelyet nagy valószínűséggel alkalmaznak. Az együttműködő és együtt-tervezett projektek segítenek továbbá:

- **Nagyobb elkötelezettség:** A közösségi irányítású projektek előnye, hogy az egyének úgy érzik, hogy szerepük van a projektben.
- **Meghosszabbodó időtartam:** Azon projekteknél, amelyeknél monitoring utókövetés szükséges, a helyi közösségek nagy valószínűséggel vállalják azt.
- **Jobban informált közösség:** A közösségi bevonás a projekttervezés fázisában elősegíti, hogy a helyi tudás már kezdeti fázisban is megjelenik a projektben és így sokkal szilárdabb célokat lehet kitűzni.
- **Kiterjedtebb projekttervékenység:** A helyiek bevonása segít további problémák és a monitoring lehetőségek azonosításában, amelyet más érintett felek nem láthattak előre.

A Rákospatak civil tudomány projekt

A Rákospatak a Duna 44 km-es mellékvízfolyása, amely Budapest területén torkollik a folyamba. Korábbi nagy árvizek következtében erősen szabályozták, lesüllyesztették a vízgyűjtő, csatornába kényszerítették a patakot és szinte teljesen lecsapolták a környező vizes területeket Budapesten belül. A civil tudomány projekt célja a Rákospatak ökológiai helyreállításának elősegítése, ezért az érintett felekkel közösen tervezett civil tudomány mini projekteket jöttek létre, hogy a vízminőség, a part menti területek természetessége, valamint meghatározott védett fajokat nyomon követése céljából.

Az általános tudás és érzékenység a Rákospatak, a vízminőséggel és a biológiai sokféleséggel kapcsolatban alacsony, így a helyreállítási gondolatok is leginkább az ember-központú megoldásokat preferálják. A civil tudomány projekt nem csupán adatok gyűjtő, hanem növelte az érzékenységet és általános tudást a patak, és az ökológiai revitalizációval kapcsolatban.

Néhány megállapítás a Rákospatak civil tudomány projekttel kapcsolatban:

- A civil tudomány projekt együtt-tervezése nulláról indult szakértők támogatásával;
- Az érintett felek tapasztalatai és a szakértők segítségével egy ökológiai helyreállítási javaslatcsomag került kidolgozásra;
- A projekt növelte az általános érzékenységet a Rákospatak, és annak állapotával kapcsolatban: rossz a vízminőség és egyes fontos védett fajok jelen voltak a területen;
- Jobban tájékozottak, elkötelezettek és tudatosabbak lettek a civilek az ökológiai helyreállítás iránt;
- Felkeltette az érdeklődést a tudományos témák iránt a civilekben;
- Új lendületet adott a helyreállítási projektnek.

A Rákospatak civil tudomány projekt eredményeit 2022. május 26-án mutatták be egy a Rákospatak ökológiai helyreállításáról szóló konferencia keretében, ahol a főbb érintettek részt vettek, többek között döntéshozók is, mint például Budapest Főpolgármestere, Karácsony Gergely, és Rákospalota Polgármestere, Horváth Tamás.

További információkat olvashat, hogy miképpen lehet sikeres civil tudomány projekteket kialakítani a vízfolyások vizsgáldkódásával és helyreállításával kapcsolatban az alábbi weboldalon angol nyelven: <https://catchmentbasedapproach.org/learn/citizen-science-volunteer-monitoring/>

Fontos lépés a sikeres civil tudomány projekt kezdeményezések létrehozásakor, hogy a projektek hatásainak mérése, hogy azok előrehaladását, eredményeit jól lehessen kommunikálni. Jogi kereteket ezen a téren, hogy miképpen lehet jól nyomon követni a civil tudomány projektek hatásait a MICS projekt weboldalán, a mics.tools található.

Figure 5 Citizen science in Romania

Știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor pentru monitorizarea râurilor

Cum știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor poate sprijini gestionarea și restaurarea râurilor

Ce este știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor?
Știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor este definită ca participarea voluntarilor (adică a persoanelor care nu sunt implicate ca parte a angajării lor) la cercetarea și monitorizarea mediului. Acest lucru are dublul beneficiu, de a permite indivizilor să contribuie la cercetarea științifică, în timp ce, se implică și educă oamenii.
Proiectele științifice pentru cetățeni sunt adesea dezvoltate de profesioniști (de exemplu, manageri de proiect care lucrează la ONG-uri sau alte organizații ce se ocupă cu conservarea) faunei sălbatice, care definesc scopurile și obiectivele proiectelor. Voluntarii contribuie apoi cu date la proiect. Această abordare, denumită știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor contributivă, nu este utilizată pe scară largă în România. Există multe forme diferite de știință realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor pe care ați putea dori să le luați în considerare.

Oamenii și comunitățile locale joacă un rol critic în toate fazele managementului și restaurării râului; știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor, este un aspect al acestui lucru.
Cetățenii implicați în activitățile științifice efectuează cercetări privind calitatea mediului, monitorizarea râurilor, lucrări de restaurare, conduc proiecte și multe altele. Munca desfășurată de cetățenii de știință ajută la sprijinirea deciziilor de management al râului.
Implicarea cetățenilor în proiectele fluviale are adesea impacturi multiple, nu numai pentru cei implicați, ci și asupra societății, mediului și științei însăși.

De ce să folosim știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor, pentru a sprijini gestionarea și restaurarea râurilor?
Creșterea urbanizării și schimbările climatice înseamnă că râurile noastre sunt supuse unei presiuni din ce în ce mai mari și ne confruntăm cu decizii dificile cu privire la cum să le gestionăm cel mai bine, în special pe termen lung. Știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor ne poate ajuta să facem față acestor provocări prin:

- **Designul proiectului:** Implicarea comunităților locale în faza de design a proiectelor asigură asimilarea cunoștințelor locale cât mai devreme posibil. Acest lucru va îmbunătăți calitatea și rezistența proiectelor de restaurare. **Colectarea datelor:** Prin colectarea datelor științifice (prin activități de monitorizare), cetățenii de știință ajută la stabilirea stării actuale a sistemelor fluviale și ne permit să luăm decizii informate de management.
- **Eficient din punct de vedere al costurilor și durabil:** Implicarea comunității poate ajuta la dezvoltarea scopului și ambiției proiectelor de restaurare a râurilor; știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor este o modalitate eficientă din punct de vedere al costurilor de a efectua monitorizarea pe termen lung.
- **Implicarea și educația:** proiectele științifice pentru cetățeni oferă un mijloc de a implica o gamă diversă de oameni și de a le crește cunoștințele, conștientizarea și implicarea.
- **Reconectarea oamenilor cu natura:** Implicarea cetățenilor ajută la reconectarea comunităților locale cu natura și generează un sentiment de apartenență în administrarea râurilor.
- **Viziune și leadership:** cetățenii de știință își pot asuma responsabilitatea pentru conducerea proiectelor și pot oferi perspective care ajută la îmbunătățiri viitoare.

Contributiv, colaborativ sau co-creat?
Există trei abordări principale ale științei realizate cu ajutorul cetățenilor. Acestea includ:
Contributiv: cetățenii sunt implicați doar în colectarea datelor. Designul proiectului, scopurile și obiectivele și activitățile sunt decise de oamenii de știință/ managerii de proiect.
Colaborativ: cetățenii contribuie cu date și pot ajuta la proiectarea proiectului, dar scopurile, obiectivele și activitățile sunt decise de oamenii de știință/ managerii de proiect.
Co-creat: cetățenii sunt implicați activ în toate etapele proiectului, lucrând alături de managerii de proiect pentru a identifica scopurile și obiectivele și pentru a conveni asupra activităților, pe lângă faptul că sunt implicați în colectarea datelor.

Selectarea căreia dintre aceste abordări este benefic de a fi utilizată, va depinde de natura proiectului de cercetare. Pentru proiectele care implică monitorizarea mediului care au o utilizare finală clară a datelor, modelul contributiv va fi probabil cel mai aplicabil format. Cu toate acestea, proiectele colaborative și co-create ajută la:

- **Un angajament mai mare:** proiectele conduse de comunitate beneficiază de faptul că indivizii simt că au o porțiune dedicată exclusiv lor, în proiect.
- **Longevitate crescută:** acolo unde este necesară monitorizarea repetată, comunitățile vor fi probabil mai dispuse să se angajeze în acest sens.
- **Mai bine informat:** implicarea comunității în planificarea proiectului într-un stadiu incipient înseamnă că cunoștințele locale pot fi luate în considerare într-un stadiu incipient și un set mai solid de scopuri și obiective formulate.
- **Domeniu de aplicare sporit:** Implicarea locală poate ajuta la identificarea unor probleme suplimentare sau a oportunităților de monitorizare neprevăzute de alte părți interesate.

Case Study – Monitorizarea Zonei umede Carasuhat

Studiul nostru de caz se numește “Zona umedă Carasuhat”, situată pe teritoriul biosferei Deltei Dunării. Se pot observa schimbări majore ce au început acum câțiva ani, în momentul în care entitățile care au în administrare locația au hotărât să restaureze zona la starea sa inițială, naturală. Principalele noastre ambiții pentru activitățile de știință realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor au fost selectate pentru a ajuta și sprijini procesul de restaurare și pentru a monitoriza progresul și rezultatul soluțiilor implementate. Astfel, unul dintre obiectivele principale este de a sensibiliza actorii locali (care include populația locală) cu privire la soluțiile verzi și de a stabili o schemă de monitorizare care poate fi foarte ușor accesibilă pentru toată lumea.

Cele mai importante aspecte sunt:

- Am reușit să inițiem și să menținem discuții bilaterale constructive între părțile interesate și entitățile ce dețin capacitatea de decizie în zonă, având sprijinul tuturor celor implicați.
- O mai bună aliniere între eforturile de monitorizare ale cetățenilor și organismele de reglementare;
- Organizarea de ateliere de lucru care a concluzionat necesitatea îmbunătățirii în continuare a relațiilor dintre părțile interesate și entitățile de management și am convenit și asupra parametrilor care trebuie monitorizați în locație.
- Părțile implicate au fost deplin de acord cu privire la importanța factorului de calitate a apei și a evoluției continue a procesului de restaurare.
- Colectarea eficientă (din punct de vedere al costurilor) de seturi de date pe termen lung;
- Creșterea nivelului de detectare și raportare a evenimentelor disturbatoare;
- Creșterea sentimentului de implicare și apartenență în rândul cetățenilor, referitor la mediul înconjurător.

Pe perioada desfășurării proiectului, au fost observate o serie de rezultate cheie, cum ar fi necesitatea unui flux mai bun de documente care poate scădea nivelul birocrăției dintre părțile interesate și factorii de decizie precum și disponibilitatea populației locale de a se implica în activitățile de monitorizare a calității mediului înconjurător. Datorită acestor rezultate se poate observa o tendință de creștere a implicării cetățenilor interesați de știință ce doresc să facă parte din diferite acțiuni cu impact pe viitor asupra mediului înconjurător.

Mai multe informații despre cum să stabiliți proiecte științifice de succes prin implicarea cetățenilor pentru managementul și restaurarea râurilor pot fi găsite pe site-ul web [Catchment Based Approach \(CaBA\)](#).

Un pas important în dezvoltarea inițiativelor de succes în domeniul științei realizate cu ajutorul cetățenilor este monitorizarea impactului proiectelor pentru a promova creșterea și dezvoltarea în continuare. Pentru a obține sfaturi despre cele mai bune practici despre cum să monitorizați impactul inițiativei dvs. în știința realizată cu ajutorul cetățenilor, vizitați site-ul web al proiectului [Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science \(MICS\)](#).

4 Conclusions

The main result of the MICS project is an integrated platform, where metrics and instruments are available for use by anyone involved in a citizen-science project wanting to understand its impact, at any stage of a project lifecycle

The multimedia resources described in this document will enable the successful dissemination and exploitation of these tools well beyond the end of the MICS project.